

ASPECTS REGARDING THE EVOLUTION EXPECTATIONS OF THE HEALTHCARE SYSTEM AFTER THE GLOBAL PANDEMIC CRISIS OF 2020

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Abstract

Purpose – Great crises bring change that triggers evolution. The purpose of this paper is to present evolution expectations of key people acting in the medical field regarding managerial and scientific evolutions, that will appear in the decades that will follow triggered by the greatest global healthcare crisis faced in the modern times.

Methodology/approach – In order drive the research, there were developed a set of instruments consisting in extended interviews and questionnaires. The results fare from different point of views - hospital managers and key decision makers in the medical system, teaching professors and researchers in Medicine and Medical devices. In the study are also represented the next generation of medics and researchers - students from medical universities.

Findings – The parties involved in this study highlights some trends in research and development in the field of medicine, medical technology and management in medical branches. More important is the fact that due to its major stress caused by the pandemic and all the effort invested in fighting the pandemic, the humanity has a great chance to evolve.

Research limitations/implications –This study was conducted with focus on responders from Bucharest and Cluj, two important medical and university cities in Romania.

Practical implications – Extended studies regarding the expected evolution should be intensified by governments, universities, research institutions and international alliances or organizations acting in this field. We identified a great economic and social opportunity for Romania.

Originality/value – We designed several instruments in order to organize the results of our study regarding the evolution expectations after the actual global healthcare crisis. As we are looking into the future, the subjective answers from qualified responders offer possible perspectives of the progress that will follow the 2020 Global Pandemic.

Key words: Global healthcare crisis, managerial and medicine evolution.

Introduction

What role will robots play in medicine in the future? How will the pharma industry evolve? Will telemedicine and other technologies enable non- contact treatment possibilities? What will be the status of medical professionals in the future? What chances should Medical University Cites exploit? Will life-prolonging technology change our lifestyle? How will the access to healthcare look like in the future? Will humanity achieve the next big technical and social evolutionary step after the COVID-19 global medical crisis?

We look to questions regarding the future that will follow the COVID-19 greatest global healthcare crisis of all modern times. We are targeting responders already involved in different stages in the healthcare system. We discussed, interview and received answers from a variety of targeted responders. This variety consists from experienced hospital managers and key decision makers in the healthcare system

which acted in the first line during the first stages of the pandemic to experienced researchers and professors at medicine universities and of course, the students, representing the next generation medics, researchers, professors and decision makers in the healthcare system.

Methodology

Our study was conducted in three stages:

1. The first one consists in conducting extensive interviews with managers and key decision makers as well as with specialists involved in research in medicine and medical technology. The goal of this stage was to identify and structure the topics.
2. The second stage, consists in developing questionnaires and gathering data from teaching professors and students. Although they have the same structure and target the same topics, we developed different questionnaires for the two different categories.
3. The third stage was to compare and analyze the results in order to present the relevant conclusions of this study.

Results

The study has two parts, the first one concentrates on the technical expected evolution in the medical field, while the second part reflects the expected evolution from social point of view, like the role and status of medical professionals in future and general access to high level treatments.

The first part presents the general idea of expected evolution from technical point of view, as well as some fields where evolution is highly expected.

Almost every crisis is followed by evolution in technology, society etc. In this case, we speak of the greatest global healthcare crisis in modern times. We wanted to investigate the opinion of our responders regarding the expected evolution in medical technology after COVID-19 crisis.

Our first significant result is the difference of expectation levels between the younger generation represented by students at medical university versus the experienced teachers and researchers. 64% of the students expect a high and very high evolution in medical techniques and technology in following years as a result of the crisis, while only 42% of the experienced teachers and researchers expect a high and very high improvement and also, the same percentage expect a moderate rate of evolution in medicine and medical technology. Another difference comes in the rate of 23% of young students who think that the COVID-19 crisis will not accelerate evolution, compared with less than 15% of experienced professionals who believe the same.

For now, we will note, that 75% to 85% of all responders expect moderate or high to very high rates of progress in medicine and medical technology after the COVID-19 healthcare crisis. More than this, the younger generation is more polarized between very high to very low expectations while the experienced generation has moderated to high expectation, as presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Comparison between generations regarding the expectations on evolutionary progress in medicine and medical technology after the COVID-19 crisis

Our next result goes deeper into the fields of expected evolution. While anticipating important evolutionary steps in the healthcare system and medical technology, most of the key decision makers are expecting evolutionary steps in research and development and medical technology, medical field and teaching system in medicine. Almost 67% of them think that the most important progress will be achieved in research and development as well as in medical technology.

Regarding telemedicine, the young generation of students again has higher expectations with 73% of them expecting high to very high progress in the next years, compared to only 50% of the experienced generation who expects high to very high progress in this field. Figure 2. illustrates the results for both categories of responders. But overall, it is obvious that both generations expect moderate to very high progress in the next years in the field of telemedicine.

Figure 2. Expected evolution in telemedicine

Regarding the role of digitalization of the healthcare system both generations consider it will grow. 94% of the student's generations and 92% of the experienced generation consider that the role of digitalization will become more important.

Now, taking into consideration the major impact that the COVID-19 global healthcare crisis has on almost all sectors and with respect to the financial sector, we were looking on possibilities that could become economic drivers to recover after the crisis. Like major infrastructure programs and IT investments who helped recover the economy in past crises, the investments in life prolonging technology might become the new economic drivers.

Regarding the investment in life prolonging technology and evolution in this field, the younger generation is very confident, 91% of them think that great progress will be obtained in the next years in this field. In contrast, only 57% of the professors and researchers think likewise. Although the experienced generation is more moderate in this topic, the general result that the majority of them, together with the large majority of the next professional generation think at life prolonging technology with such hope, might actually be the starting point for increasing research and development budgets on all levels in this direction.

The second part, is dedicated to sociological aspects like the role of medical professionals in society, expected resources for research in medical field, general access to high quality medical treatments and the impact of the COVID-19 healthcare crisis on the professional planning of the new generation of medicine students, like international careers, involvements in research projects and even the impact on choosing their further specialization.

While many specialists in many branches fear that their role will diminish as automation, robots and artificial intelligence (AI) step in, we were looking on how the experienced but also the young generation of medical students look at the position of the medic in the society, after the COVID-19 crisis. We forced the answer by replacing one of the obvious possibilities, like the role of the medic will diminish, with the expression: automation will take over many of attribution of medical staff'. In this order the results from the young generations and the experienced one are almost similar at a distance of few percentages.

The overall interpretation of the combine result presented in Figure 3. illustrates that most of our responders see an improvement of the status and role of the medics in the future.

Figure 3. The role of the medic in the Society

Only 13% of them prefer to concentrate on the threats of their position due to automatization, robotics and digitalization. Therefore, we could presume, that the attractiveness of this profession could attract high potentials from future generations. Also, the education system in this field, could become of great interest, not only due to its impact on the healthcare system, but also regarding the impact on the economy. As university education is expensive and taking into consideration that the Romanian medical university system has a very good international reputation, the education system could become national strategic interest. Furthermore, half of the students are considering an international career. This is very relevant for the high quality of the educational system, and the fact that the students feel confident in the education they receive, education that would allow them to build international careers. On the other hand, as the education in medical field is very consistent and the studies usually take more years, by the time of this study, only 13% of the students consider that the COVID-19 global healthcare crisis impacted their choice regarding the future medical specialization. This is presented in Figure 4.

Figure 4. COVID-19 impact on choosing the specialization

Regarding the confidence in financial investment in medical research, 57% and 28% of the experienced professionals expect more and considerably more investments, while the students generation is more sceptic, as 52% of them do not expect an increase of resources for medical research, as shown in Figure 5. In contrast, the skepticism of the young generation of medics do not demotivates them regarding their involvement in research activity, as 41% of the students wish to take part in research projects, and 32% percent of them consider this option as very likely.

Figure 5. Financial investment in medical research

Our last result comes as a great surprise. When asking both experienced and young generation regarding the further the access to high level medical treatment, 76% of the young generation and 71% of the experienced generation consider that top level medical treatment will only be available for those who can afford them, while the minority considers that most of the people will have access to advanced treatment and medical technology. Analyzing this result with the expectation that medical technology will evolve with an accelerated rate, could bring great differences between different healthcare systems.

Discussion and conclusions

Our first conclusion is related to the general high expectation level from medical specialists regarding the evolution both technological and social in the field of medicine and healthcare systems. The polarized younger generation of medicine students compensates the lack of experience with enthusiasm.

The idea of having separate instruments for each generation helps us identify the differences, but also helps us to consolidate the results. For example, all the generations expect high rate evolution in medicine, digitalization, telemedicine. Although we have to mention that such decisive results might also be a consequence of the high rate of evolution in the past years in the field of digitalization but also a consequence of the physical distancing imposed by the COVID-19 pandemic.

The greatest gap between generations appears when discussing about life prolonging technology. While in this case, the young generation seems very optimistic, most of the experienced specialists still think, great evolutionary steps will be reached. Since 91% of students and 57% of experience professionals expect this evolution, it appears to be a good direction for research investments.

With respect to the educational system, we can conclude that this vital sector in our society might also become of higher importance since it's great performance, half of the students consider themselves ready and consider to build an international career and most of them are determined or think at getting involved in research projects, although the experienced generation has higher expectation to get more resources or medical research after the COVID-19 crisis.

While taking into consideration, that in the opinion of more than three quarters of all responders, the society will become more polarized, and only those who will afford will have access to high level medical treatment, following question appears: what are the chances in Romania?

One answer could be a national strategy on development and major investments in the educational, specific medical education and healthcare system. The general expensive but particularly in Romania, the very performant medical educational system, could become one of our greatest assets on international scale. It is not a secret that Romanian medical universities are highly appreciated worldwide and many foreign students attend their courses. It could become one of our most valuable export products, if we consider education as a product.

On the other hand, since we expect only the rich citizens to have access to the highest medical treatments, one of the solutions to ensure large-scale high-level access in a country with the development status like ours, is to concentrate resources in education, research and production in this specific field. This conclusion could become the research topic of a national scale for those who are interested.

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